

Versatile synthesis of *N*-substituted lactopyranosyl formamidines by desulfurization of the corresponding thiocarbamides

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Abstract : 1-Hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl formamidines were easily synthesized by desulfurization of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-*H*/aryl thiocarbamides with Raney nickel. From the synthetic point of view, the protocol can be considered and efficient for the synthesis of lactosylated formamidines in moderate to excellent yields.

Keywords : Desulfurization, Raney nickel, lactosyl thiocarbamides, lactosyl formamidines.

Introduction

Formamidines are the important class of compounds because of their utility as synthetic intermediates, biological and pharmaceutical agents¹. The uses of formamidines in organic synthesis have been quite diversified, including roles as auxiliaries in asymmetric synthesis², protecting groups for primary amines³, electrophiles⁴ and support linkers in solid phase synthesis⁵. Beside these formamidines have been found use as antimalarial⁶, anticancer, antitumor activity⁷, antifungal agents, anti-inflammatory⁸, anti-edema, anti-hypersensitive, ultra violet light absorbers⁹ and in many other ways. On the other hand *N*-glycosylated compounds are known for their potential activities as pharmaceutical and biological agents.

General routes to formamidines and related compounds are dominated by condensation (amine + formamide)¹⁰ and exchange (amine + formamidine acetals)^{3,11} routes. The previously known methods of formamidine synthesis had not been applied to, or were ineffective in the incorporation of sugar moiety, which may be expected to enhance the biological activity of such structures. Raney nickel¹² have been reported as promising dethiating agents for 2-thiobarbiturates, the yields range from high to moderate. Raney nickel has distinct advantage over other desulphurating reagents. The aromatic rings, acids, nitriles, esters etc. are found mostly undisturbed while the

related sulphur compounds are desulphurated. Further Raney nickel has been reported as a convenient and an efficient reagent for the desulfurization of mercaptans, sulfides, sulfoxides, sulfones and thioketals. It has also been reported as a chemoselective reagent for deoxygenation of sulfoxides and selenoxides. In view of its versatility and ease of handling, it was decided to explore its application for the desulfurization of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-*H*/aryl thiocarbamides **2** to yield novel 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl formamidines **1**.

Results and discussion

Considering the high potential in synthesis of newer glycosyl formamidines and as they will provides access to newer formamidines with wide scope at the formamidine position. It was exciting to synthesize 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl formamidines **2a-1** by reductive desulfurization of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl thiocarbamides **1a-1** by Raney-Ni in toluene medium. The solid gave charring test and non-desulphurisable. The purity of compounds was checked by TLC. Optical rotation and R_f value of the product was also recorded.

The IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, Mass spectral analysis¹³⁻¹⁷ and elemental analysis (Table 1) clearly indicated the product and assign the structure as 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl formamidines.

Table 1. Characterization of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl formamidines (**2a-l**)

Sr. no.	Reactants 1a-l	Product 2a-l	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	$[\alpha]_D^{32}$ (0.1, in CHCl_3)	Found (Required) N	R_f (Pet. ether : EtOAc) (1 : 1)
1.	-3-H-	2a	75.24	84	+26.88	4.21 (4.22)	0.67
2.	-3-phenyl-	2b	84.08	95	+45.26	3.38 (3.79)	0.91
3.	-3- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	2c	79.25	130	+86.25	3.61 (3.72)	0.56
4.	-3- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	2d	82.36	125	+58.68	3.65 (3.72)	0.93
5.	-3- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	2e	78.02	132	+63.14	3.68 (3.72)	0.48
6.	-3- <i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	2f	82.01	110	+53.21	3.60 (3.62)	0.86
7.	-3- <i>m</i> -Cl-phenyl	2g	77.69	113	+72.36	3.58 (3.62)	0.66
8.	-3- <i>o</i> -anisyl-	2h	83.63	103	+66.68	3.62 (3.64)	0.89
9.	-3- <i>m</i> -anisyl-	2i	87.26	105	+68.76	3.60 (3.64)	0.84
10.	-3- <i>p</i> -anisyl-	2j	85.39	100	+86.37	3.57 (3.64)	0.68
11.	-3- <i>m</i> -OH-phenyl	2k	83.04	135	+56.17	3.68 (3.70)	0.74
12.	-3- <i>p</i> -OH-phenyl	2l	79.08	122	+44.01	3.65 (3.70)	0.63

Scheme 2

Where, R = (a) H; (b) phenyl; (c) *o*-tolyl; (d) *m*-tolyl; (e) *p*-tolyl; (f) *o*-Cl-phenyl; (g) *m*-Cl-phenyl; (h) *o*-methoxy phenyl; (i) *m*-methoxy phenyl; (j) *p*-methoxy phenyl; (k) *m*-hydroxy phenyl; (l) *p*-hydroxy phenyl.

Ac = -OCH₃.

Experimental

Melting points of the synthesized compounds were recorded on electro thermal melting point apparatus are uncorrected. Specific rotations of the newly synthesized compounds were measured on Equip-Tronic digital polarimeter model no. EQ 800 at 30 °C in CHCl_3 . IR spectra

were recorded on a Model - Agilent Cary 630 FTIR spectrometer. ¹H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz, FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as an internal reference. The MS spectra were recorded on a Agilent 6520 Q-TOF (ESI-HRMS) mass spectrometer and ¹³C NMR were recorded in CDCl_3 .

Purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography using Merck silica gel coated aluminum plates and petroleum ether : ethyl acetate as eluent.

Materials :

All solvents and reagents were commercial and used without further purification.

Preparation of 1-hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactopyranosyl-3-H/aryl thiocarbamides 1a-l :

1-Hepta-*O*-acetyl-β-*D*-lactopyranosyl-3-*H*/aryl thiocarbamides were prepared by earlier known method¹⁸ by interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl-β-*D*-lactopyranosyl isothiocyanate and aryl amines (Scheme 1).

Preparation of Raney nickel (W-2) :

The required Raney nickel (W-2) was prepared by earlier reported method¹⁹ by action of sodium hydroxide solution on powdered Ni-Al alloy.

Preparation of 1-hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactopyranosyl-3-H/aryl formamidines 2a-l :

To a toluene solution of Raney nickel (W-2; 15.0 g in 100 ml) in a three necked 250 ml round bottom flask, fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel. The toluene solution of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl-β-*D*-lactopyranosyl-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (7.70 g; 0.01 mol in 50 ml) **1a** was taken in a dropping funnel and added to the Raney nickel in a round bottom flask with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was heated gently over heating mantle for 150 min with TLC monitoring. After the completion of reaction the reaction mixture was filtered hot to remove wasted Raney nickel (nickel sulphide). The solvent was distilled off on the rotary evaporator to afford a semisolid which on triturating with petroleum ether 60–80 °C for several times afforded faint yellow solid. The latter were then recrystallized from ethyl alcohol to afford pure solid (**2a**).

Similarly, when the reactions were extended to other lactosyl thiocarbamides **1b-f** the corresponding lactosyl formamidines **2b-f** was obtained (Scheme 2).

Spectral analysis :

2a : IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3415 (N-H), 2439 (C-H), 1749 (C=O), 1519 (C=N), 1372 (CN), 1225 (C-O), 1056 (characteristics of lactose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–2.0 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.9 (1H, s, C-H proton), 0.8 (2H, s, N-H proton);

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 169–170 (C=O carbons), 61–77 (lactosyl carbons), 31.64 (CH₃-CO carbons), 20–21 (C-H carbon).

2b : IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3407 (N-H), 3023 (aromatic C-H), 1749 (C=O), 1656 (C=N), 1373 (C-N), 1223 (C-O), 1056 (characteristics of lactose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.3–7.0 (5H, m, aromatic protons), 6.9 (1H, s, NH), 5.2–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–2.0 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.9 (1H, s, C-H proton); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 169–170 (C=O carbons), 129–114 (Ar-C), 61–77 (lactosyl carbons), 29.82 (CH₃-CO carbons), 20–21 (C-H carbon); Mass (*m/z*) 739 (M⁺+1), 619, 559, 331 (base peak), 168.

2c : IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3024 (aromatic C-H), 2968 (aliphatic C-H), 1748 (C=O), 1654 (C=N), 1373 (C-N), 1223 (C-O), 1057 (characteristics of lactose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.3–7.0 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.9 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.8 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.3–2.0 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.6 (1H, s, C-H proton), 1.2 (3H, s, methyl protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 169–170 (C=O carbons), 136–114 (Ar-C), 60–74 (lactosyl carbons), 29.67 (CH₃-CO carbons), 20.86 (methyl carbon).

2d : IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3401 (N-H), 3019 (aromatic C-H), 1750 (C=O), 1650 (C=N), 1384 (C-N), 1216 (C-O), 1066 (characteristics of lactose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.2 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.7 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.7 (1H, s, C-H proton), 1.2 (3H, s, methyl protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 169–172 (C=O carbons), 74.46–83.10 (lactosyl carbons), 29.81 (CH₃-CO carbons), 20.97 (C-H carbon); Mass (*m/z*) 619, 559, 331 (base peak), 168.

2e : IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3397 (N-H), 3022 (aromatic C-H), 1749 (C=O), 1644 (C=N), 1384 (C-N), 1218 (C-O), 1064 (characteristics of lactose); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.2–7.0 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.9 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.3–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons) 1.5 (1H, s, C-H proton), 1.1 (3H, s, methyl protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 169–171 (C=O carbons), 142–114 (Ar-C), 66–84 (lactosyl carbons), 21.11 (CH₃-CO carbons), 20.53 (C-H carbon).

2f : IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3350 (N-H), 3025 (aromatic C-H), 2968 (aliphatic C-H), 1748 (C=O), 1652 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 1227 (C-O), 1054 (characteristics of lac-

tose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.5–7.3 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.6 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–2.0 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.2 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 169–171 (C=O carbons), 133–128 (Ar-C), 74.64–83 (lactosyl carbons), 29.78 (CH_3 -CO carbons), 20.60 (C-H carbon).

2g: IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3476 (N-H), 3024 (aromatic C-H), 2982 (aliphatic C-H), 1748 (C=O), 1648 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1219 (C-O), 1057 (characteristics of lactose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.3 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.2 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.2 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 168–171 (C=O carbons), 137–128 (Ar-C), 75.70–82 (lactosyl carbons), 29.59 (CH_3 -CO carbons), 20.45 (C-H carbon); Mass (m/z) 619, 559, 331 (base peak), 168.

2h: IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3400 (N-H), 3023 (aromatic C-H), 1750 (C=O), 1657 (C=N), 1373 (C-N), 1221 (C-O), 1056 (characteristics of lactose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.2 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.8 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.8 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.8 (3H, s, OCH_3 protons), 1.2 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 168–172 (C=O carbons), 150–101 (Ar-C), 60–77.66 (lactosyl carbons), 55.74 (OCH_3 carbon), 20.47–20.70 (C-H carbon).

2i: IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3400 (N-H), 3024 (aromatic C-H), 1748 (C=O), 1654 (C=N), 1375 (C-N), 1224 (C-O), 1053 (characteristics of lactose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.3–7.2 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.7–6.2 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.7 (3H, s, OCH_3 protons), 1.1 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 168–181 (C=O carbons), 160–113 (Ar-C), 60–77.66 (lactosyl carbons), 55.08 (OCH_3 carbon), 20.35–20.69 (C-H carbon); Mass (m/z) 619, 559, 331, 168, 123.

2j: IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3405 (N-H), 3019 (aromatic C-H), 1749 (C=O), 1655 (C=N), 1384 (C-N), 1215 (C-O), 1063 (characteristics of lactose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.2–7.0 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.9–6.8 (1H, s, NH), 5.3–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.8 (3H, s, OCH_3 protons), 1.2 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 168–170 (C=O

carbons), 153–114 (Ar-C), 60.93–77.66 (lactosyl carbons), 55.55 (OCH_3 carbon), 20.51 (C-H carbon).

2k: IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3400 (N-H), 3022 (aromatic C-H), 1751 (C=O), 1650 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1218 (C-O), 1057 (characteristics of lactose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.3 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.9 (1H, s, OH), 6.3 (1H, s, NH), 5.4–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.2–1.9 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.2 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 168–171 (C=O carbons), 157–101 (Ar-C), 60.90–77.66 (lactosyl carbons), 29.48 (CH_3 -CO carbons), 20.36 (C-H carbon); Mass (m/z) 619, 559, 331 (base peak), 168.

2l: IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3408 (N-H), 3020 (aromatic C-H), 1750 (C=O), 1650 (C=N), 1384 (C-N), 1217 (C-O), 1060 (characteristics of lactose); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 7.3 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 6.7 (1H, s, OH), 6.5–6.2 (1H, s, NH), 5.4–3.7 (14H, m, lactosyl protons), 2.1–2.0 (21H, m, acetyl protons), 1.2 (1H, s, C-H proton); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 169–171 (C=O carbons), 150–115 (Ar-C), 60.95–77.66 (lactosyl carbons), 29.73 (CH_3 -CO carbons), 20.56 (C-H carbon).

Conclusion

N-Substituted lactopyranosyl formamidines derivatives were synthesized and characterized for their structure elucidation. Various chemical and spectral data supported the structures. The method adopted in this investigation is simple, efficient and inexpensive and is useful in synthesizing pharmacologically important molecules.

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Patkar *et al.* : Versatile synthesis of *N*-substituted lactopyranosyl formamidines by desulfurization *etc.*

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